

RECYCL3D

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DELIVERABLE D1.1: Recycled Aggregates and 3D printing technology: production requirements, printability and way forward

Author(s):	João Pacheco ^a , Karyne Santos ^a , Pawel Sikora ^b , Szymon Skibicki ^b , Mateusz Techman ^b , Karol Federowicz ^b , Oscar Reales ^c , Manuel Vieira ^d , Bruno Leporace-Guimil ^e , Nikola Tošić ^e , Marco Pepe ^f
Institutions:	^a c5Lab – Sustainable Construction Materials Association ^b WPUTS - West Pomeranian University of Technology in Szczecin ^c UFRJ - Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro ^d LNEC - Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil ^e UPC – Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya ^f UniSA – University of Salerno

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Abstract

RECYCL3D is a transnational project that includes eight institutions from six countries and aims at promoting the use of fine recycled aggregates (fRA) as a secondary raw material for concrete produced with additive manufacturing technology (3D printed concrete). This report is its first deliverable (D1.1).

The main goal of this report is to systematize knowledge on fine recycled aggregates and 3D printed concrete so that all members of the consortium are acquainted with both topics and informed decisions are made in future tasks. Both 3D printing of concrete and the use of recycled aggregates in concrete are strategies with potential to promote the sustainability of the construction sector. RECYCL3D aims at combining them since there are operational and technical reasons to believe that concrete for 3D printing is a particularly suitable material for the incorporation of fine recycled aggregates. Since concrete printing technology and the use of recycled aggregates in concrete are two very different topics, the consortium gathers experts from each of the fields and aims at synergies between partners.

This report:

- Discusses the use of recycled aggregates in the context of the circular economy;
- States the requirements of 3D printing technology;
- Overviews a database on concrete mix designs for 3D printed concrete made from data sourced from 100 publications;
- Appraises the few publications found by the authors on the use of fine recycled aggregates in 3D printed concrete;
- Describes the general production process of recycled aggregates, as well as that of a technologically-advanced CDW plant;
- Presents properties of fine recycled aggregates from mixed CDW with the grading that will be used in the project.

The report finishes with recommendations for the next work package of the project: WP2 – - *Processing, selection & classification of fRA*, and WP3 – *Early-age behaviour*, in what concerns the type of fRA that will be tested and incorporated in concrete.

The report argues that research on 3D printed concrete made with fine recycled aggregates is scarce and does not explore the possibility of recycled aggregates improving some of the properties needed for concrete 3D printing technology (namely, the potential for improved buildability). The analysis of the production process of common CDW plants immediately concluded that the project needs to resort to laboratory-produced recycled aggregates and it was agreed that fine recycled aggregates produced from both concrete waste and ceramic waste will be tested.

The grading of the aggregates will be 0/2 and fines will be removed. A subtask of WP3 will be the assessment of the influence of the incorporation of recycled fines in the properties of 3D printed concrete.

List of acronyms

3DPC	3D printed concrete
AM	additive manufacturing
CDW	construction and demolition waste
fRA	fine recycled aggregates
MRA	mixed recycled aggregates
OPC	ordinary Portland cement
RA	recycled aggregates
RAC	recycled aggregate concrete
RCA	recycled concrete aggregate
RMA	recycled masonry aggregate
SCM	supplementary cementitious materials
WA	water absorption
w/b	water-to-binder

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1 Preliminary remarks

1.1 Introduction and motivation

This report, titled *Recycled Aggregates and 3D printing technology: production requirements, printability and way forward* is the first deliverable of the ERA-MIN3 transnational project RECYCL3D - Recycled aggregates for 3D printed concrete structures.

This project aims at promoting the use of fine recycled aggregates (fRA) as a secondary raw material for concrete produced with additive manufacturing technology – also designated as 3D-printed concrete.

Fine recycled aggregates result from the processing of construction and demolition waste (CDW). This process is carried out to recover CDW as recycled aggregates (RA) and is typically made by sorting, crushing and size screening operations [1]. fRA are necessarily produced during this process; however, their market uptake is low and end uses for fRA are scarce and mostly for operations deemed as downcycling [2] – backfilling (a lower value type of recovery) and road construction and minor civil works. Part of fRA are also landfilled, an operation that does not constitute recovery and that should be avoided. The lack of higher end recovery options compromises the full circularity of the CDW management industry.

Simultaneously, 3D printing technology for concrete production is a novel production process that is associated with less construction waste and absence of formwork [3-5]. Provided that geometry is optimized, concrete volume is minimized and the overall environmental impact of a concrete product is smaller than that of a conventional concrete element.

The use of fRA as a secondary raw material for the production of 3D-printed concrete is a good option, mainly due to the following aspects:

1. Most 3D-printed concrete mixes have a high content of fine aggregates and no coarse aggregates are used. Fine natural aggregates are scarce in some regions and their extraction is associated with environmental cost, damage to ecosystems and infrastructure, risking human life [6];
2. The production rhythms and production process of 3D-printed concrete are not an obstacle for the use of fRA. That is not the case for other products, such as ready-mixed concrete whose production rhythm and need to transport the already-mixed concrete to the construction site create additional challenges related to the quality control and assurance.

The main goal of RECYCL3D is the development of 3D printed concrete made with incorporation of fRA, including design and production guidelines as well as sustainability validation. The project involves 8 institutions from 6 countries and combines expertise in RA and recycled aggregate concrete with expertise on 3D-printed concrete.

The different institutions are experts on different topics, therefore the main motivation of the report is to contextualize all institutions with both the potential of fRA for use in concrete and with 3D printing technology and mix design.

The report fundamentals and prepares future work of the project by characterizing the current market conditions and properties of fRA, describing basic aspects and requirements related to 3D concrete printing technology and presenting research and considerations on the use of fRA on 3D-printed concrete.

Afterwards, recommendations for the next work packages WP2- Processing, selection & classification of fRA, and WP3 – Early-age behaviour, are made.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of this report are the following:

1. Provide all partners of the project with basic information and context related to fRA and 3D-printed concrete technology and mix design;
2. Understand the current status of CDW recovery as fRA and the main properties expected from fRA produced from mixed CDW and from concrete waste;
3. Understand the potential of fRA as a secondary raw material for 3D-printed concrete;
4. Provide recommendations for the next two work packages of the project.

In order to achieve these objectives, the following tasks are made:

1. Appraisal of the current market uptake of fRA and the potential of fRA for use in concrete products;
2. Appraisal of printability requirements and of 3D printing technology for concrete production;
3. Discussion of the potential of fine RA in 3D-printed concrete, through state-of-the-art discussion;
4. Presentation of the general production process of RA in CDW plants and of an illustrative database with basic properties of fRA produced in the visited / surveyed plants;
5. Recommendations for WP2 - Processing, selection & classification of fRA, in what concerns the type of fRA that will be tested;
6. Recommendations for WP3 – Early-age behaviour, in what concerns the concrete mix design for the 3D-printed concrete mixes.

These tasks are the basis for the structure of the report, with each chapter clearly aligned with a specific task.

2 State-of-the-art on fine recycled aggregates

Managing the waste generated by human activity is a worldwide challenge. In 2020 according to Eurostat [7], the total waste generation in the EU by all economic activities and households amounted to 2.151 million tones or 4.808 kg per capita. The share of different economic activities and of households in total waste generation in 2020 is presented in Figure .

In the EU, construction contributed 37.1 % of the total European generation of 2020 and was followed by mining and quarrying (23.4 %), manufacturing (10.9 %), waste and water services (10.7 %) and households (9.5 %). The remaining 8.4% was waste generated from other economic activities, mainly services (4.5 %) and energy (2.3 %). Due to the large scale of its activity and in addition to being very important for the economy of several countries, the construction sector has a significant impact on

the environment as it causes a huge natural resources consumption and generates significant amount of waste, as shown in Figure for EU members countries. Therefore, the use of recycled aggregate from CDW, instead of conventional aggregates, has a twofold environmental advantage: it decreases the consumption of natural resources and reduces the land needed for waste disposal [8-13].

Figure 1: Waste generation by economic activities and households, EU, 2020 (%share of the total waste) Source:Eurostat (online data code: env_wasgen) [7].

Figure 2: Eurostat Construction and Demolition Waste by the EU countries Source:Eurostat (online data code: env_wasgen) [7]

2.1 Existing regulations on the use of RA

The enormous generation of CDW has resulted in several EU-wide sustainable development policies geared to tackling climate change, including the *Strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth* [14] and the *Next steps for a sustainable European future* [15]. These strategies and commitments include encouraging production procedures that embrace circular and more sustainable production and decision- e.g. by recovering waste as secondary raw materials, reducing raw material over-exploitation and maximizing material life cycles [16].

However, whilst recycling is often cited as the best way to manage CDW, there are still several obstacles to using RA in construction, such as:

- Lack of confidence of clients and contractors;
- Uncertainty as to its environmental benefits;
- The absence of regulation, and in particular design guidelines, lack of standards and specifications for the design of RAC and RAC structures that concrete producers or designers can take into account;
- Low quality of the final product, owing to lack of knowledge and/or market demand for CDW recycling plant owners to justify investment;
- Distance between construction and demolition sites and recycling plants in countries where CDW plants do not have broad geographical coverage;
- Lack of a consistent supply of good quality RA that can satisfy existing demand.

In order to encourage and promote the use of RA, government agencies the world over have often introduced levies and legislation in an attempt to overcome barriers, with varying degrees of success. The variability of building construction methods naturally means that RA sourced from construction and demolition activities will vary in quality and composition, which tends to result in construction materials of varying quality [9, 17].

Even in countries with high concrete waste recycling rates, the market uptake of RA remains low and its use is still mostly relegated to low value applications such as backfilling, road base or sub-base. This is a sub-optimal solution since it typically leads to “down-cycling” [2]; for example, when recycling structural concrete and using the produced RA in lower-value applications.

This is especially important considering that close to 50% of concrete produced in the EU is reinforced structural concrete. Therefore, the objective of the construction industry and concrete community in particular, must be the wider application of RA in producing structural recycled aggregate concrete (RAC). This has led to wide initiatives in the research community, such as the RECYBETON national project in France, aimed at the industrial upscaling of RAC [18].

On behalf of RILEM Technical Committee 37-DRC, Nixon prepared a state-of-the-art report on the use of recycled concrete aggregates in the production of concrete, covering the period 1945–1977 [19]. A second state-of-the-art report on recycled aggregate concrete was prepared by Hansen, covering developments between 1978 and 1985 [20]. And the third state-of-the-art report was an updated version of the second state-of-the-art report including developments in the period 1985–1989 [21]. In 2002, ACI Committee 555 reported information on evaluating and processing waste concrete for production of aggregates suitable for reuses in concrete constructions [22].

The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) has dealt with RA through standards on aggregates for concrete EN 12620 [23] and concrete specification EN 206 [24]. Nonetheless, the effect

of RA incorporation into recycled aggregate concrete in terms of mechanical and structural behavior has not been comprehensively taken into account. However, a significant body of literature now exists on recycled aggregate concrete and this knowledge is now being transferred into design guidelines and codes. The International Federation for Structural Concrete (*fib*) and CEN have undertaken initiatives to incorporate recommendations for structural design of recycled aggregate concrete into the new Model Code 2020 and in the second generation of Eurocode 2 (EN 1992-1-1) [18].

As a result of the research conducted to date, some countries have enacted legislation on the use of recycled concrete aggregate (RCA), in concrete manufacture. **Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania.** summarizes part of the legislation in place on the use of RCA in concrete, listing particle size allowed and maximum replacement ratios. The table includes RCA (shaded cells) whose composition ($5\% \leq R_b\text{-masonry waste} \leq 30\%$) determines its classification as a mixed recycled aggregate in some international standards [16]. It should be noted that, although certain standards allow the replacement of only one fraction (e.g. coarse), the percentage of replacement may be expressed in terms of total aggregate (coarse + fine) and this should be considered carefully when applying each standard.

As understood from **Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania.**, the common denominator in all the specifications for concretes in strength classes C25/30 to C40/50 is the stipulation of a ceiling on the amount of natural coarse aggregate that can be replaced by coarse RCA (15% to 60%, depending on quality, design strength of the structural reinforced concrete and exposure class). Total replacement of NA with high quality RCA is allowed only in Australia, China, Denmark, Switzerland and in the RILEM recommendations. Whereas total replacement of NA is subject to no concrete strength class limitations in China or Switzerland, in Australia it is limited to class C25/30, in Denmark to class C40/50 and under the RILEM provisions to class C50/60. This table is illustrative and does not cover all requirements for an RA to be used in concrete. For instance, the environmental exposure class is often a limiting factor.

The use of fine RCA for structural concrete manufacture, in turn, is addressed in the legislation in place only in China (30% to 100% of natural aggregate), Denmark (100%), Korea (30%), Japan (100%) and United Kingdom (20%). RCA of lower quality or deemed MRA on the grounds of composition can be used as a 100% replacement in structural concretes with a design compressive strength of C25/30 in Australia, whereas in Germany replacement is limited to 35% in C35/45. In all other countries appraised, the use of fRA is restricted to non-structural concrete, even when the fRA is produced solely from concrete waste. Most countries limit the use of RA to the coarse fraction only and at replacement ratios of 20% to 30% (typically of the coarse fraction, but in some cases of the total aggregate content) whilst the use of medium-to high quality fRA in structural concrete, in turn, is addressed in only 22% of the standards appraised [8-10, 16].

These limitations justify the need to find alternative cementitious products that would allow the incorporation of fRA. This is especially relevant when considered that fRA accounts for 25% to 50% of the RA generated at CDW management plants and is usually landfilled or used in low grade applications, despite its potential recovery in the concrete chain [16, 18].

Table 1: Legislation on the use of recycled aggregate in concrete [3,8].

Country	Aggregate type	Composition	Fraction	Max. replacement (%)	Concrete type	Strength class
Australia AS 1141.62 / HB 155:2002	RCA (Class 1A)	-	Coarse	30	Structural	C40/50
	MRA (Class 1B)	Rb < 30%		100	Structural	C25/30
China GB/T-25177	RCA – Type I	-	Coarse	100	Structural	No limit
	RCA – Type II	-		30	Structural	C40/50
	RCA – Type III	-		30	Structural	C25/30
	RCA – Type I	-	Fine	100	Structural	C40/50
	RCA – Type II	-		30	Structural	C25/30
Korea KS-F-2573	RCA	-	Coarse	30	Structural	27 MPa
		-	Coarse + Fine	30	Non-Structural	21 MPa
Hong Kong CS-3:2013/ HKBD 2009/ WBTC-No. 12	RCA	-	Coarse	20	Structural	C25/30
		-		100	Non-Structural	C35/45
Japan JIS-5021/ JIS-5022/ JIS-5023	RCA – HQ	-	Coarse	100	Structural	C45/55
		-	Fine	100		
	RCA – MQ	-	Coarse	100	Structural	C35/45
		-	Fine	100		
Belgium PTV 406-2003/ NBN B 15-001	RCA – Type A	Rc + Ru > 95, Ra < 1	Coarse	50, 30, 20*	Structural	C30/37
	MRA – Type B	Rc + Ru > 70, Rb < 30, Ra < 5	Coarse	20	Non-Structural	C20/25
Germany DIN 4226-101, DafStb	RCA – Type A	Rc + Ru > 90, Rb < 10, Ra < 1	Coarse	45, 35, 25*	Structural	C30/37
	MRA – Type B	Rc + Ru > 70, Rb < 30, Ra < 1	Coarse	35, 25*	Structural	C30/37
Italy NTC-2008	RCA 1	Rc + Ru > 95	Coarse	30	Structural	C30/37
	RCA 2			60		C25/30
	MRA	-	Coarse	15	Non-Structural	C45/55
Denmark DS 2426/ DCA No. 34	RCA 1	Rc + Ru > 95	Coarse	100	Structural	10 MPa
	RCA 2		Coarse + Fine	100		C40/50
	MRA	Rc + Ru < 95	Coarse	100	Non-Structural	C20/25
Netherlands NEN-5905	RCA		Coarse	20	Structural	C55/67
			Coarse	20	Structural	C40/50
Portugal LNEC – E471	RCA 1	Rc + Ru > 90, Rb < 10, Ra < 5	Coarse	25	Structural	C40/50
	RCA 2	Rc + Ru > 70, Rb < 30, Ra < 5	Coarse	20	Structural	C35/45
	MRA	Rc+Ru+Rb>90 Ra<10	Coarse	100	Non-structural	
Switzerland MB - 2030	RCA 1	Rc < 25, Ru > 75, Rb < 5, Ra < 1	Coarse	100	Structural	No limit
	RCA 2	Rc > 25, Ru < 75, Rb < 5, Ra < 1		100		
	MRA	Rc + Ru < 95, Rb > 5, Ra < 1		100		
United Kingdom BS 8500-2	RCA	Rb < 5, Ra < 5	Coarse / Fine	20	Structural	C40/50
France NF P 15-545	RCA 1	Rc + Ru > 95, Rb < 10, Ra < 1	Coarse	60, 30, 20	Structural	No limit
	RCA 2	Rc + Ru > 90, Rb < 10, Ra < 10		40, 15		
	MRA	Rc + Ru > 70, Rb < 30, Ra < 10		30, 5		
Spain EHE-08	RCA	Rb < 5, Ra < 1	Coarse	20	Structural	C40/50
EN 206 (Informative annex that is superseded by national regulations)	RCA	Rc + Ru > 95, Rb < 5, Ra < 1	Coarse	50, 30	Structural	No limit
	MRA	Rc + Ru > 70, Rb < 30, Ra < 5		50, 20		C30/37
RILEM	RCA	Rc < 100	Coarse	100	Structural	C50/60
Brazil NBR 15,116	RCA	Rc + Ru > 90	Coarse / Fine	100	Non-Structural	-
	MRA	Rc + Ru < 90				

Notes. – **RCA:** recycled concrete aggregate; **MRA:** mixed recycled aggregate; **HQ:** high quality; **MQ:** medium quality; **LQ:** low quality; **Rc:** concrete and bound mortar; **Ru:** unbound aggregate; **Rb:** masonry material; **Ra:** asphalt; and ***Replacement ratio by exposure class.** The higher the exposure class, the lower the replacement ratio.

2.2 Classification of RA

According to [17], the quality of an RA recycled aggregate may be, as a first approximation, be related to its composition. Therefore, three main types of RA are defined: crushed concrete, crushed masonry, and mixed CDW [17].

Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCA): Concrete is found in most RA because it is the most used construction material in structural applications and accounts for the majority of CDW. Organizations in various countries have developed specifications which include a definition for RCA. Many of them seem to agree that to be considered an RCA, the aggregate must comprise a minimum of 90% by mass of Portland cement-based constituents (concrete and/or mortar) and unbound stone (in fact, a natural aggregate). In EN 12620 [23], concrete and mortar constituents are classified by the designation Rc and unbound stone Ru. It is intended that this will lead to grades of RA in which: (i) $Rc+Ru \geq 90\%$, (ii) $Rc+Ru \geq 70\%$, and (iii) $Rc+Ru < 70\%$, where the quality of the RA is determined by the recycled brick (Rb) content and by the possible presence of other, unintended contaminants [17].

Recycled Masonry Aggregate (RMA): Masonry rubble is a collective designation for various mineral building materials resulting from the construction and demolition of buildings and civil engineering structures. This family of materials may include aerated and lightweight concrete blocks, ceramic bricks, blast-furnace slag bricks and blocks, and sand-lime bricks. Masonry rubble often contains mortar rendering and burnt clay materials such as roofing tiles and shingles. It is composed of a minimum of 90%, by mass, of all the materials mentioned above. RA with high recycled brick content are commonly produced by best-practice recycling centers in which a concerted effort has been made to separate concrete and asphalt to other stockpiles [18].

Mixed Recycled Aggregates (MRA): This material is composed of crushed and graded concrete and masonry rubble. The resulting aggregate is a mixture of two main components obtained from the beneficiation of CDW. Some specifications establish its composition as less than 90%, by mass, of Portland cement-based fragments and NA. In other words, it may contain several other common CDW materials such as masonry-based materials (ceramic, light-weight concrete) [17].

2.3 Properties of fine recycled aggregates

In this section, fRA is to be understood as fine recycled aggregates produced from crushed concrete that contains a minimum of 90% by mass of fragments based on Portland and NA cement. The fRA is as a two-phase material (aggregates and binder paste - Figure 3:). At the microscale, there is a third phase in the fRA, which is composed of the interfaces between aggregates and binder. These interfaces influence the physical properties of fRA [25].

Figure 3: Different types of ITZs prepared with different fine aggregates: a) UHPC with natural fine aggregate (NFA), and b) UHPC with NFA partially replaced by recycled fine aggregate (FRA) [25].

The way in which fRA are generated will have a direct impact on the particle size distribution and quantity of the fines. For instance, the increased number of crushing steps will increase the content of fine material. Compared to natural sand, fRA contain significantly more fines and tend to be more angular and with rougher surfaces. Regarding surface texture, it has been shown that the coarse RCA are as rough as or rougher than crushed natural aggregates. Whilst there are no studies which compare surface roughness of fRA and that of fine natural aggregates, the findings suggest that, due to the adhered cement paste patches, surface roughness of fRA is higher than of river sand. This will affect the rheology of the concrete due to increased resistance of non-spherical and rough shapes to flow [25].

The water absorption (WA) and density of aggregates are the key parameters in concrete mix design. Researchers have observed that the immersion period needed to fully saturate an fRA should be longer than 24 h and that the evaluation of the water absorption of fRA is strongly influenced by the procedure (type and duration of immersion, in water or paste), size fraction of fRA, specimen weight and agglomeration of small particles. In addition, it is difficult to judge the moisture state of fRA accurately.

In Density and water absorption of fine natural aggregates and fRA [25]. **Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania.** WA and density values for fRA and natural sand reported in the literature are summarized. The differences between fRA and fine natural aggregate result from higher WA. The reported WA values for fRA vary between 4.28 and 13.1%, with an average of 8.4%. The reported WA values for natural fine aggregate vary between 0.15 and 4.1%, with an average of 1.1%. In addition, the fRA has lower density than fine natural aggregates. The obtained saturated-surface-dry densities of fRA are between 1630 and 2560 kg/m³, with an average of 2295 kg/m³. The densities of natural fine aggregate vary between 2530 and 2720 kg/m³, with an average of 2637 kg/m³. The scatter with respect to WA and density values between different studies is caused by variations in the quality of parent concrete, which is often unknown (water-to-cement ratio, type and amount of cement, aggregates origin and gradation, etc.) and of the crushing process used, as well as the intrinsic scatter of the properties [25].

In the concrete mix design, besides water absorption, the moisture state and the content of aggregates are largely important. The moisture content of aggregates has an important effect on the rate of water absorption of aggregates since the amount of water they will absorb during mixing and setting will be smaller when aggregates are dry(er). Therefore, the moisture content influences the total water content of a recycled aggregate concrete mix design to a large extent and needs to be accounted for in the mix design. Generally, since fRA particles are rougher, porous and have larger water absorption, the moisture content of fRA will be higher than that of natural aggregates [25].

Table 2: Density and water absorption of fine natural aggregates and fRA [25].

Authors	Fine natural aggregate		fRA	
	Density (SSD)	Water absorption (24hs)	Density (SSD)	Water absorption (24hs)
	kg / m ³	w, %	kg / m ³	w, %
Evangelista & De Brito (2004, 2007, 2010)	2564	0.80	2165	13.10
Carro-López et al., (2015)	2720	1.00	2300	9.30
Khatib (2005)	2650	0.80	2340	6.25
Sarhat (2007)	2640	4.10	2330	12.50
Levy & Helene (2007)	2650	1.80	2320	10.30
Lee (2008)	2600	0.80	2280	10.35
Lee (2008)	2600	0.80	2390	6.59
Kou & Poon (2009)	2620	0.88	2300	11.86
Vegas et al., (2009)	2670	0.34	1630	7.6
Vegas et al., (2009)	2670	0.34	2110	8.09
Vegas et al., (2009)	2670	0.34	2140	6.73
Vegas et al., (2009)	2670	0.34	2130	7.84
Vegas et al., (2009)	2670	0.34	1980	6.65
Vegas et al., (2009)	2670	0.34	2200	7.18
Dapena et al., (2011)	2630	3.56	2460	7.26
Yaprak et al., (2011)	2650	1.22	2310	4.28
Zega 30	2630	0.90	2560	8.50
Pereira 35	2620	0.19	2230	10.19
Kim & Yun (2014)	2650	1.00	2290	5.83
Kim & Yun (2014)	2650	1.00	2150	7.95
Le 79	2640	0.50	2410	6.80
Cartuxo et al., (2015, 2016)	2678	0.15	2460	7.09
Zhao et al., (2015)	2660	1.05	2540	7.54
Yildirim et al., (2015)	2660	1.99	2450	6.22
Mardani-Aghabaglou et al., (2015)	2610	0.67	2440	6.81
Bogas et al., (2016)	2568	1.68	2156	9.05
Bendimerad et al., (2016)	2600	1.20	2100	10.70
Fan 27/57	2653	1.30	2347	8.90
Fan 27/57	2653	1.30	2404	6.60
Güneyisi et al., (2016)	2660	0.55	2260	12.80
Kumar et al., (2017)	2670	0.44	2080	11.91
Evangelista & De Brito (2017, 2018)	2580	1.07	2210	10.43
Ho et al., (2018)	2600	2.88	2360	9.43
Yacoub 76	2530	2.30	2440	6.86
Delsaute & Staquet (2019)	2600	1.20	2100	10.65
Ali (2019)	2680	1.45	2430	7.89
Mardani-Aghabaglou et al., (2019)	2610	0.68	2410	6.95
Nedeljković et al., (2020)	2647	0.30	2543	7.00

*SSD: saturated and surface-dried density

2.4 Short and long-term properties of cast concrete containing fine recycled aggregates

As aforementioned, fRA have different particle size distributions, moisture states, water absorption and tend to be angular with rougher surfaces compared to natural sand. These differences will significantly affect the packing density, the fresh/short properties (workability) and hardened properties (strength) of the new concrete mixtures.

Workability

Low workability (reduced slump and slump-flow values) is mostly reported for concrete with fRA due to higher water demand of fRA than the same concrete made with river sand. Figure presents the relationship between the concrete slump and the incorporation ratios of fRA. Explanations for this are that fRA absorbs more water from the mix than natural aggregates due to its higher water absorption and that fRA are rougher and have higher specific surface than NA [26] (due to their constituents and because fine aggregates are usually rolled sand, while most fRA are produced with single jaw crushing). Moreover, the influence of fRA on workability is typically larger than what is observed when coarse RA are used because smaller fRA have higher water absorption than coarse recycled aggregates from the same source concrete. In order to obtain desired workability of mortars and concretes with fRA it is necessary to increase the mixing water to account for the water absorbed by the fRA (before or during the mixing process) or to use superplasticizers. Studies clearly indicate that the evaluation of workability depends on the moisture state of the fRA, their water absorption of fRA, the fRA incorporation ratio and the mixing procedure. Although researchers have given a lot of reasonable explanation concerning the complex flow behavior through combination of experiments and theories there is no universal approach defined to obtain and maintain satisfactory workability of mortars/concretes with fRA [25, 27].

Figure 4: Relationship between fRA concrete and slump from similar w/c ratio [26].

Compressive strength

Compressive strength is one of the parameters most scrutinised by researchers. Several studies have focused on the use of fRA in normal-strength and self-compacting concretes. The findings for the influence of fRA on the compressive strength of concrete are not consensual: it was higher, the same or lower compared to control mix [26-28], but most commonly decreases when equal workability of RAC and NAC are a design objective. It is clear that the compressive strength is rather sensitive to the high replacement level of fRA (100%), irrespective of the binder composition or cement content. This reduction is attributed mainly to the increased water content in concrete mixes with fRA needed to achieve the same workability to that of concrete with natural fine aggregates; increase in the fRA replacement increases the effective water-to-cement ratio of the mixes. Consequently, poor interface bond with the surrounding paste matrix is formed because of the deposition of water near the interface zone. These works have suggested that compressive strength, similar to workability, strongly

depends on the moisture state of fRA, the water-to-cement ratio and the fRA replacement ratio [10, 16, 25] [10, 16, 25].

Tensile strength

Though less important than compressive strength to the performance of structures in terms of ultimate limit states, tensile strength plays a fundamental role in their response to serviceability limit states. Most authors agree with the fact that the increase of the replacement ratio of NA with fRA reduces the tensile strength; however, the value obtained is still acceptable, especially for reasonable levels of the replacement ratio (30%) [16, 29]. Nevertheless, when silica fume and superplasticizers were used, the properties of high-performance concrete using fRA was found that the addition of them increased tensile strength. In addition, the study [30] found that RA obtained from moderate- or high-strength concrete with original granite or basalt aggregates appeared effective component for HPC, i.e. the performances of HPC with natural aggregates or RA are similar [10, 25].

Modulus of elasticity

Similarly to conventional concrete, in the case of cementitious products used in 3D printing, the modulus of elasticity is strongly related to the stiffness and content of aggregates, the stiffness of the cementitious paste and their porosity and bond [31]. For small incorporation ratios, the modulus of elasticity is not expected to be significantly reduced since the influence of RA is proportional to their incorporation ration [10, 29]. Nevertheless, superplasticizers could mitigate the negative effect of incorporating fRA since they allow a reduction of the amount of water in the concrete mix [25], increasing the stiffness of the cementitious paste. The 3D printing of concrete uses a large amount of fine material, so when a high percentage of fRA is used, a relevant negative effect is expected. However, even though this could depend on the source of the fRA as well as the recycling technique and storage, the latter could be mitigated with the superplasticizers on the market that will decrease the amount of water applied to achieve good workability. Consequently, decreasing the amount of free water in the cement paste and improving the performance of the matrix with fRA.

Shrinkage

Studies based on the influence of the fRA replacement ratio, the source of fRA and the mineral additions on drying shrinkage of concrete with fRA have showed that the drying shrinkage and creep of mortars and concretes with fRA, are significantly affected. Higher drying shrinkage of concretes with fRA were attributed to the lower elastic modulus of fRA (due to the presence of old cement mortar) and their higher water absorption, leading to a greater change in the water content in the concrete [27]. Due to higher water demand of fRA compared to natural fine aggregates, not only drying, but also the plastic and autogenous shrinkage rate and extent will be different compared to shrinkage of conventional concrete mixtures [10, 25]. A few studies showed that the drying shrinkage of concrete with fRA can be reduced: by pre-saturation of fRA, by addition of supplementary cementitious material (SCM), by removal of ultrafine fractions from fRA. Yildirim et al. [32] showed that saturation of fRA mitigates the drying shrinkage of concrete with fRA. A moisture level of 50% of the saturation for a fRA content of 50% yielded a concrete with satisfactory performance. The synergistic influences of SCM with fRA on the shrinkage characteristics of SCC are observed and found that the ternary blend binder (ordinary Portland cement (OPC), fly ash and silica fume) effectively control the shrinkage strain of concrete made with fRA than the binary blend mixes (OPC and fly ash) [25]. Other studies performed on the shrinkage of RAC, especially concerning their coarse fraction and

the general finding has been a significant increase in the shrinkage of the RAC mixes vs. conventional concrete [10].

Creep

Similar to shrinkage, several studies have shown that creep was also affected by incorporation of fRA. A significant increase of the creep is observed when using fRA, especially at very early age. The creep of concrete with RA is expected to be higher than in conventional concrete since it has lower modulus of elasticity because of the lower stiffness of the RA [10].

Cartuxo et al. [33] found that creep deformation increased up to 129% at 28 days and 154% at 91 days in concrete with 100% fRA compared to concrete with 100% natural fine aggregates. This study has noted the importance of superplasticizer on creep deformation. It has been suggested that superplasticizer decreases the internal moisture transmission and diffusion to external environment, improving the hydration of cement and consequently increasing strength and decreasing creep. Bravo et al.[27] showed a large variation of the shrinkage and creep results depending on the source of the RA. As authors suggested, this tendency was expected, since each type of fRA has its own composition, depending on the parent concrete.

In summary, the fRA have physico-chemical characteristics depending on the original design and history of the concrete as well as the recycling technique and storage. These physico-chemical characteristics have an influence on the performance of the concrete mix as well as the hardened concrete. Currently, little knowledge, no guidelines or regulations exist to make optimal use of these characteristics of the fRA in order to make high quality concrete at the same or reduced cement contents. Therefore, large scale introduction and optimal use of fRA in new concrete is hampered because the risks on expected concrete performance are uncertain and increased cement contents to compensate water demands of fRA result in higher costs and CO₂ emissions.

Knowledge on the relation between the fRA treatments and the physico-chemical characteristics of the fRA, as well as knowledge on optimal packing and interaction with cement in order to keep cement contents low for high performance concrete and knowledge on the microstructure and expectance for long term behavior of the new concrete should be research priorities.

3 Printability requirements and 3D printing technology

3.1 Principles of 3D printing and its requirements

3D printing, also called additive manufacturing, of cementitious composites is one of the fastest developing branches of construction in the world. Its main advantages are the ability to reduce construction time, material consumption and labour.

The 3D printing is performed by stacking successive layers of material on top of each other using computer-controlled robots. The method allows to construct complex spatial structures. Over the past 10 years, the number of research teams and commercial companies interested in 3D printing of construction grew exponentially. This interest has been the catalyst for an intensification of scientific work that has focused on the sustainability aspects of additive manufacturing.

Compared to traditional methods of construction, the use of highly automated 3D printing increases the construction speeds and lowers labour, thus reducing the total cost of investment. Additionally, the 3D printing does not require traditional formwork, therefor allowing for intricate and complex geometries at lower costs [34-36].The lack of formwork and architectural freedom of printed

structures requires dedicated materials and methods. The additive manufacturing can be divided into two groups of methods: extrusion-based 3D printing and injection in a cementitious binder substrate (particle-bed 3D printing) [35, 37].

The first developed extrusion-based method was called contour crafting and consists in printing along the contour of the designed parts. This method was developed in the late 1990s by Behrokh Khoshnevis from the University of Southern California in the USA [38].

In the case of cementitious composites used in 3D printing, the key properties are slightly different from those of traditional concretes. Majority of researchers determined such properties as pumpability, extrudability, buildability, compressive strength (green strength) and open time [39].

One of the main differences in the composition of concrete for 3D printing (3DPC) compared to traditional concrete is the lack of coarse aggregate. Coarse aggregates (>4 mm) are not suitable in most cases of printing due to technical limitations of pumps and the small cross-section of individual layers of concrete (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Examples of 3D printed concrete elements

Another noticeable difference between 3D printing mixes and traditional concrete is the amount of cement and total binder content in the composition. Traditional concrete has cement content usually ranging between 300 kg/m^3 and 420 kg/m^3 . Therefore, its total amount of binder is lower than in 3DPC mixes, as is its content of fine aggregates and chemical admixtures. Mineral additives and various types of reactive materials are often used in printing to modify the rheological properties affecting pumpability, extrudability or load-bearing capacity of the fresh mix. Their use also increases the thixotropy of the mix which is considered beneficial for additive manufacturing [39-41].

Exemplary mixture compositions of 3DPC are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Composition of 3D printed mixes

	Binder	water/binder w/b	binder/aggregate b/a	Aggregate	Admixtures [% wc.]
Perrot et al. [42]	Cem	0.41	1.00	0-0.1 mm	0.30
Le et al. [43]	Cem/FA/SF 0,7:0,2:0,1	0.28	0.66	0-2 mm	1.00
Nerella et al. [44]	Cem/FA/SF 0,26:0,26:0,48	0.42	0.65	0-2 mm	3.00
Zhang et al. [45]	Cem/SF/NC 0,96:0,02:0,02	0.50	1.00	0-1 mm	0.26
Paul et al. [46]	Cem/FA/SF 0,41:0,39:0,20	0.40	0.59	0-1 mm	1.00
Mechtcherine et al. [47]	Cem/FA/SF 0,59:0,23:0,18	0.30	0.40	0-8 mm	0.84
Kazemian et al. [48]	Cem/FA 0,9:0,1	0.43	0.44	0-2.36 mm	-

Cem – cement; FA. – fly ash; SF – silica fume; NC. – nanoclay; % wc. – % of cement weight

3.2 Literature study of mixture designs of 3DPC

In order to establish typical ranges of raw materials for 3DPC mix design, a literature review was performed. For the literature survey, the online databases of Scopus and Web of Science were used and search was performed using following keywords sets:

1. "3D print**" AND "concrete" AND "cement"
2. "3D print****" AND "mortar" AND "cement"
3. "3D print**" AND "mortar" AND "cement"
4. "3D print****" AND "concrete" AND "cement"
5. "3DPC" AND "cement"
6. "3DCP" AND "cement"

The collection initially was composed of 125 publications. After pre-screening process 25 publications were excluded from the database since they did not meet the requirements (e.g. papers that lack the description of the mixture compositions tested or review articles). The final outcome was of 100 publications. Depending on the parameter under analysis, between 165 and 369 mixes were analysed.

Figures 6-7 present the information on w/b ratio and total binder content in 3DPC mixtures, confirming that 96% of all evaluated mixes consists more than 500 kg/m³ of binder.

Figure 6 Percentage distribution of the water-to-binder (w/b) ratio used in 3DPC mixtures (total amount of mixes evaluated: 165)

Figure 7. Percentage distribution of the total cement content used in 3DPC mixtures (total amount of mixes evaluated: 165)

Figure 8 depicts the typical admixtures and additives used as a binder constituent for 3DPC mixes. To ensure proper fresh characteristics of the material mostly silica fume/micro silica, fly ash and furnace slags are used.

Figure 8. Percentage distribution of the types of additives and admixtures used in 3D printed mixtures (total amount of mixes: 369).

The 165 mixes were checked for their relative cement content in relation to the total binder content (Figure 9). The mean content of cement to the total binder content is of 76% and its coefficient of variation is 22%. This mix design parameter has large variability but is not dependent on the total binder content (the R^2 of the linear relationship between cement content and the relative ratio of binder content is of 0.7%). The minimum relative content of cement to binder is of 40%, and 31 of the 165 mixes had relative cement content of 90% or larger. This analysis shows that there is no clear preference towards using higher content of SCMs when the binder content increases.

Figure 9. Percentage distribution of the cement content contribution to the total binder content in 3DPC mixtures.

The typical water-to-binder (w/b) ratio of 3DPC mixes lies in the 0.2-0.4 region to ensure the proper fresh characteristics of the material (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Percentage distribution of the water-to-binder (w/b) ratio used in 3DPC mixtures (total amount of mixes evaluated: 214)

Figure 11 presents size of aggregates used for 3DPC confirming that, in the vast majority of the mixes, the aggregate size does not exceed 2 mm, thus mostly fine aggregate is used in the 3DPC due to pump limitations and material stability in the fresh state.

Figure 11. Percentage distribution of the maximum aggregate size used in 3D printed mixtures (total amount of mixes: 218)

Summarizing the analysis presented in this section, it is found that:

1. Mixes developed for 3DPC have much higher binder content than that typically found in concrete mix design. 95% of all mixes appraised have binder content above 500 kg/m^3 , 60% of all mixes have binder content above 800 kg/m^3 and 25% have binder content above 1000 kg/m^3 ;
2. The w/b ratio of 3DPC is low and is usually in the range of 0.30 – 0.35;
3. 82% of all mixes use solely fine aggregates. Furthermore, in 80% of cases, the maximum aggregate size is below 2 mm.

4 Fine recycled aggregates and 3D printing technology

There are few references concerning the recovery of CDW as aggregates in 3D printing concrete. This section summarizes the main findings reported in the literature regarding the application of recycled concrete aggregates in 3D printable concrete. This type of aggregate presents greater water absorption compared to natural aggregates due to the content of old paste adhered to the stone fraction of the RA (Figure 12). The attached mortar directly influences the workability and mechanical behaviour of cementitious materials. Such effects will be scored below regarding the use of CDW in 3D printing concretes. Similar observations are also valid for RA produced from unsorted CDW, since other constituents (e.g. ceramics) are also porous.

Figure 12. Comparison between: natural aggregate (siliceous sand); recycled aggregate produced from concrete waste (stone + mortar); a recycled aggregate produced from unsorted CDW (in this case, a porous ceramic particle)

This section concerns the incorporation of RA produced from concrete waste only since:

1. This type of RA has better properties in comparison to those produced from unsorted CDW waste;
2. Very few research on the use of RA in 3DPC exists and it only concerns the use of fRA produced from concrete waste.

A group of researchers from Tongji University in Shanghai studied the properties of concrete for 3D printing, with partial or total replacement of natural aggregates by fRA and with the addition of concrete waste filler in place of cement [49-54]. The studies [50, 54] evaluated the behavior in the fresh state of 3DPC using fRA instead of natural sand. In [50] incorporations of 25 and 50% of fRA were used and it was observed that the fRA has little influence on the mechanical behavior of the fresh concrete. On the other hand, for resting times longer than 90 min, the greater the amount of fRA, the faster the green strength developed. This behavior was attributed to the higher water absorption of the fRA, which decreases the w/b ratio of the 3DPC.

The ability to print concrete with 100% fRA was verified in [54], evaluating its fluidity, extrudability, printing window and strength in the fresh state. The use of 100% fRA was found to decrease the fluidity of concrete and increase its rate of fluidity loss over time. However, the use of a setting retarding additive in this concrete allows meeting the printing requirements and increases the window available for the printing process, in addition to providing greater strength in the fresh state than those obtained for concretes with 100% natural sand.

The use of fRA at both replacement levels resulted in an increase in yield stress soon after mixing, as well as at 10, 20 and 30 minute intervals [55].

Furthermore, the tests analyzed the evolution of yield strength and viscosity in 5 consecutive steps with varying shear rates:

1. Low shear for 60 s at a rate of 0.01s^{-1} ;
2. Increase in shear rate up to 50 s^{-1} in 20 seconds;
3. High shear rate of 50 s^{-1} for 60 seconds;
4. Shear decrease to 0.01s^{-1} in 10 seconds,
5. Low shear for 60 s at the rate of 0.01s^{-1} .

This test procedure was adopted to simulate the different moments of pumping of the 3DPC, which, being at rest prior to pumping, will suffer disturbance and shear stress when pumped, until once extruded, it returns to rest, expressed by the last stage of the test, where the shear rate decreases to the absence of efforts.

The evolution of the yield point and viscosity is observable in steps (i) and (v) because the high shear rate applied in (ii), (iii) and (iv) will imply a dispersion of the fluid, where lower viscosity and tension values are observed. All mixtures containing fRA showed a significant increase in viscosity in relation to the reference. The mixtures while at rest prior to the increase in shear rate showed a greater increase in viscosity when compared to the post-shear period, at 150 s, when the sample returns to rest. In the case of intervals of up to 30 minutes, the authors indicate that the hydration effects are still small, while flocculation is dominant. The structure formed by flocculation is not very resistant, which justifies the recovery to a lesser degree of viscosity and yield strength after high shear rates. The authors emphasize that the use of the retardant caused that the mixtures with fRA, after the high shear rates of the test, presented the same viscosity as the reference, which indicates that the additive mitigates the effect of the aggregate in the mixture.

The rheological properties of concrete with the addition of filler produced from different types of CDW was investigated in [52]. The fillers used, all with a percentage of 20% replacement of cement, were obtained from mixed brick (CBP) of brick and concrete (MBP) and concrete (DP). The results showed that the yield stress, plastic viscosity and thixotropy increased significantly with the use of different fillers, among which, the DP provided better results in terms of the maximum layer height and stability of the fresh structure.

The mechanical behavior of concretes with the same fRA was evaluated in a study conducted by Ding et. al. [51]. The levels of replacement of fine natural aggregates by fRA were 0%, 12.5%, 25% and 50%. There was a decrease in strength for the mixtures containing fRA. The study analyzed the difference in strength of samples that were conventionally cast and compacted with that of 3D printed samples

– in the latter case, the strength was tested along each of the three axis (indicated by FX, FY and FZ). All 3D printing samples performed worse than conventionally-molded samples.

The authors argue that the decrease in strength is due to the porous structure of the fRA and the existence of microcracks in their ITZ between (old) aggregate and (old) binder paste, which was supported by scanning electron microscopy analysis. The identification of portions of old mortar paste adhered to the RA is difficult from the SEM images. The study considered the larger particle as fRA, with hydration products involved in it, with the ITZ corresponding to a thin layer between the sand and the adhered paste. Through the images, the porous structure of the adhered paste and little compact morphology were observed. Microcracks were visible between the adhered paste portion and the aggregate, possibly caused by the grinding process, which together with the porosity present in the aggregate, a lower mechanical performance of the mixture is expected with the use of this aggregate.

5 Production of recycled aggregates in CDW plants

5.1 Overview of production process

Recycled aggregates result from the recovery of CDW and the operations needed to process CDW into RA may be conducted either onsite (mobile CDW plant) or at a centralized (fixed) CDW plant. This report assumes that the plant is fixed. The technology and processes used in mobile plants are analogue to those presented here.

CDW may be mixed or it may already be well segregated prior to processing. Figure 13 shows mixed CDW and concrete waste, which is the most suitable type of CDW for RA production.

Figure 13 CDW before processing into recycled aggregates. Left: mixed CDW; right: concrete waste

Standards for conventional concrete production either recommend or impose that mixed CDW be mostly composed of concrete waste, with a moderate amount of masonry and a very small allowed amount of other constituents (e.g. glass, metals, floating materials, wood and plastics). This means that in cases in which mixed CDW arrives on site (Figure 14, left), preliminary separation must be carried out.

The preliminary separation aims at removing plastics, asbestos-containing, gypsum-based and glass materials, as well as metals, which have commercial value. If the RA are meant to be of high quality, the common option is to segregate concrete waste in a separate location of the plant and process it when a large quantity of concrete waste is ready. In this case, the RA will be produced with almost exclusively concrete waste. Preliminary separation is made with mechanical equipment as shown in Figure 14. Also, during this activity, large debris (e.g. concrete blocks) are fragmented into smaller

sizes. Contaminant materials are either recovered for other applications (e.g. energetic recovery is common in the case of plastic and wood waste) or landfilled.

Figure 14 Preliminary separation. Left: mechanical equipment used to separate waste; right: stockpile of contaminant materials removed from mixed CDW

Afterwards, the (sorted) CDW is crushed into smaller particles and sieved into different particle sizes. During this process, the particles are transported with conveyor belts and different sorting equipment is used, including magnetic separators that remove ferrous metals and automated equipment to remove lightweight materials that were not removed in the preliminary separations. Figure 15 shows some of the equipment.

Figure 15 Equipment and processes used to process CDW into recycled aggregates

The current CDW recovery in most countries is characterized by the production and use of RA in road construction. For this purpose, not only the preliminary separation is less demanding than that of RA intended for concrete, but also the particle size and grading of aggregates differ:

1. In the case of RA intended for concrete, grading must be well-controlled and the aggregates must be distributed in particle sizes that are useful to the concrete industry - e.g. fine aggregates with size 0/4 (according to the designation of EN 12620 [56], in which d/D are, respectively the minimum and maximum particle sizes in mm of an

aggregate) and coarse aggregates separated into several such fractions such as 4/8 and 8/16 or 2/6, 6/12 and 12/22;

2. When the RA are intended for road construction, grading requirements are not as stringent and aggregates have the size distribution of “all-in” aggregates – e.g. size distributions between 0/16 and 0/32 are quite common. This difference is very relevant in the current context. Since CDW management plants are typically equipped for the production of aggregates for road construction and the procurement of aggregates for concrete may be a challenge. This includes the procurement of fine aggregates, which are the topic of the project.

The next sections presents site visits to conventional CDW plants in Portugal, a visit to a technologically-developed CDW plant in Catalonia and an appraisal of the current framework for CDW management in Poland.

5.2 Visit to conventional CDW plants

Three plants near urban centres were visited:

1. PT-1 is located in Lisbon and was specifically designed to manage waste. The plant manages different waste streams and its RA are mainly intended for backfilling and road applications;
2. PT-2 is located in Lisbon and is an deactivated quarry that was converted into a CDW processing unit. It only receives CDW. Its main recovery operation is the production of RA for backfilling and road construction, but it is equipped for the production of RA for concrete (because the equipment of the quarry is still functional). Nonetheless, the production of RA for concrete is not carried out due to lack of demand;
3. PT-3 is located in Coimbra and was specifically designed to recover CDW. The plant produces RA for road construction.

The typical production of PT-1 consists in preliminary sorting to remove asbestos, gypsum, wood, plastics and metals. Afterwards, large waste blocks are immediately stockpiled for crushing and the remaining CDW passes through a rectangular sieve with 250 mm of opening, which mainly removes plastics and wood. A magnetic separator follows and then a trommel sieve produces three types of RA:

1. All-in aggregates with size 0/12;
2. All-in aggregates with size 0/32
3. RA larger than 32 mm, which undergo manual separation and pass through an air extraction system that removes lightweight materials. These aggregates are stockpiled and stored for more demanding applications.

Since this plant mostly produces aggregates for road construction, usual production includes a relevant content of masonry. Furthermore, a crusher is not used and larger waste remains stockpiled for later crushing using a mobile crusher when the stockpile becomes large. Whenever a client requests RA produced from concrete waste, a stockpile of concrete waste is used to produce these aggregates and a mobile crusher is used to crush the aggregates. The plant also owns a mobile sieve, which may be used to produce alternative particle sizes, but previous experience has shown that this crusher is not efficient in the separation of small particle sizes.

Figure 16 shows some of the equipment and processes.

Preliminary sieve to remove large particles

Magnetic separator and trommel

Production of all-in aggregates

Mobile sieve

All-in aggregate 0/12

All-in aggregate 0/32

Mechanical equipment, mobile crusher and stockpile of recycled aggregates

Figure 16 Equipment and processes used to process CDW into recycled aggregates. PT-1

In the case of PT-2, after the preliminary separation CDW undergoes a first screening stage in which all particles below 4 mm are removed from the production line and stockpiled for lower value applications or landfilling (typically, finer particles of CDW are mostly composed of soils and weak materials). Afterwards, the CDW is crushed (an impact crusher and a hammer mill crusher) and passes through two magnetic separators. After hand removal of contaminant materials, the RA are separated in different size fractions.

On most production days, two products are prepared: the RA with grading 0/4 and poor quality that are removed in the initial stage of production and all-in aggregates 0/32. However, the plant is well equipped to produce three additional particle sizes of aggregates with good quality instead of all-in aggregates 0/32. This production is seldom made (typically for research projects) due to a lack of market demand. Figure 3 already showed the crusher and sieve of this plant, as well as its area for manual separation. Additional details are shown in Figure 17.

CDW after sorting and ready for production

Lower quality aggregates (grading 0/4) and storage of other waste removed during manual separation

Bypass used to produce all-in aggregates with size 0/32 instead of sieving

General view of the plant

Figure 17 Equipment and processes used to process CDW into recycled aggregates. PT-2

The main goal of PT-3 is to recover as much CDW as possible, since this plant does not have landfilling areas. Therefore, any CDW that it receives and does not recover needs to be sent for landfilling elsewhere, constituting expense. Preliminary separation is thorough in the removal of wood, plastics, gypsum, metals and any other materials that either have recovery potential or prevent the recovery of CDW as RA.

The CDW that is used to produce RA passes through two preliminary sieves:

1. The first removes all particles with size larger than 600 mm since their size and weight may clog or damage equipment. These particles are sent to a mobile crusher;
2. The second removes all particles with size smaller than 20 mm due to their lower quality (see the description of PT-2).

Afterwards, a trommel sieve separates particles larger than 80 mm from all others. Particles with size above 80 mm undergo manual separation and then are sent to the mobile crusher. The remaining particles (between 20 mm and 80 mm) go through an impact crusher, then they pass through an air sifter to remove lightweight contaminants, and then they are separated by size into:

1. Aggregates 0/5;
2. Aggregates 5/30, which pass through an air extractor to further remove lightweight materials;
3. Aggregates 30/50, which also pass through the air extractor.

Each of these RA may be sold independently, but usually this plant sells all-in aggregates with grading 0/40. These aggregates are produced by crushing the larger particles (above 80 mm and above 600 mm) and combining them with the other fractions of RA.

Figures 18 and 19 summarize the production process of the plant.

Figure 18 CDW after preliminary separation and ready for recycled aggregate production, feeder (with preliminary sieves) and trommel. PT-3

Crusher, magnetic separator and conveyor belt

Particles that undergo manual separation

Stock of large particles for crushing

Stockpile of all-in aggregates 0/40

Figure 19 Equipment and processes used to process CDW into RA. PT-3

An overview of the plants visited is that:

1. There is a lack of market demand for RA for concrete, which leads all-plants to produce RA for road construction;
2. The previous statement implies that the production of the plants is focused on all-in aggregates composed of mixed (mostly concrete + masonry) waste;
3. All plants are capable of producing RA from concrete waste, but PT-2 is the only one whose equipment is suited to the production of aggregates with grading distributions for concrete with minimal investment, including fRA;
4. In the current state of affairs, the production of all plants requires further processing (sieving) so that fRA with grading 0/2 are produced and used as a secondary raw material for 3D-printed concrete;
5. All plants are capable to produce RA from concrete waste only, and they already do that at specific request from customers.

5.3 Visit to a technologically-developed CDW plant

Within the context of the RECYCL3D project, a CDW treatment plant was visited, located in Terrassa, Barcelona Province, Spain. The plant is operated by a leading producer of RA produced from CDW and was founded in 2006. The company also operates as a demolition company and a ready-mixed concrete producer.

Within their demolition operations the company employs selective dismantling and selective demolition. However, even under selective demolition, concrete waste streams are not separated. Furthermore, when receiving CDW from other parties, the waste is received in mixed form, Figure 20.

Figure 20 Mixed CDW stockpiled at the plant

The plant has a production capacity of 2.000 t of aggregate/day but typically operates at around 300–400 t/day. The company produces the following products (Figure 21):

1. Washed fine RCA & MRA 0/2 mm
2. Washed fine RCA & MRA 0/4 mm
3. Washed coarse RCA & MRA 4/10 mm
4. Washed coarse RCA & MRA 8/12 mm
5. Washed coarse RCA & MRA 12/20 mm
6. Washed coarse RCA & MRA 20/40 mm
7. Flocculated silts and clays

The company employs Irish and US technology in the technological process. Crushing is made by impact crushers and the fines mm (namely, silts and clays) present in recycled aggregates with size below 4 are removed in an hydrocyclone (Figure 22).

Recycled concrete sand

Recycled concrete fine gravel

Recycled concrete gravel

Recycled mixed sand

Recycled mixed fine gravel

Recycled mixed gravel

Silts and clays

Figure 21 Products available in the visited plant

Figure 22 Views of the technologically-developed CDW plant

The company is investigating the use of recycled fines in cement production and is developing EDPs for all their products – these EDPs are in the final stage of preparation. The company also has a ready-mixed plant on site and has participated in numerous projects in Catalonia, delivering non-structural recycled aggregate concrete with 100% of coarse and fine RCA and structural recycled aggregate concrete with 20% of coarse RCA (as per the limits of the Spanish structural design code [57]). The company also produces “Lego blocks” from RAC with 100% of RCA (coarse and fine), Figure 23.

Figure 23 Concrete blocks produced by the company

5.4 Poland

In Poland, an individual is not required to keep records of CDW [58]. Only construction companies and landfills have such an obligation. In order to operate a CDW landfill and treatment business in Poland, one must have the appropriate permits. CDW generated by an individual until the end of 2022 was classified as municipal waste. This state of affairs makes it difficult to estimate the actual amount of CDW in the country.

Starting in 2023, CDW collected from an individual and a business will have to be separated into at least: wood, metals, glass, plastics, gypsum, mineral waste, including concrete, brick, tiles and ceramic materials, and stones. Failure to comply with the rules could risk an administrative fine of up to 1 million PLN (212.600 € as of January 2023).

A survey [59] of the waste management market in Poland was conducted in 2010. The survey was conducted by the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection. According to the report, in Poland, in 2010 almost 16,000 businesses had a permit to collect waste, including CDW. This gives a figure of 1 enterprise per 2,400 Polish residents. New regulations coming into force in 2023 impose a limit on the level of non-recyclable waste landfilled by municipalities. For the period 2025-2029, the rate will be 30%, and will decrease to 10% in subsequent years.

With the construction market in Poland at its peak, aggregate production increased in 2018 - to 330 million tons. Only 2-3 percent of the annual demand for this material is met by imports, due to high transportation costs. Meanwhile, estimates from the Polish Aggregates Producers Association show that in 2018, natural aggregates accounted for 324 million tons of total aggregates production, for which only 6 million tons were artificial aggregates and RA [60]. However, there is no accurate data on the share of RA in relation to artificial aggregates.

The quality of RA depends on the quality of the CDW that is processed (mainly concrete, brick and asphalt). There are two ways to produce recycled aggregate:- i) at the site of demolition, construction, reconstruction, or renovation and ex situ; or ii) at recycling plants. Large savings, including on transportation costs, can be achieved when producing recycled aggregate on site.

Handling of these raw materials is problematic to record and is mostly not included in statistical data. A forecast of the size of the resource base for the production of RA is presented in the National Waste Management Plan [61]. The document provides estimates on waste generated by the construction, renovation and demolition of buildings (*Table 4*). Based on historical data (2004-2008) the share of construction materials in the total amount of waste is about 30% (the others are: 40% - scrap metal, 30% - soil and earth), in turn, the rate of waste recovery was at about 80%. Assuming an increase in the recovery rate to 90% (such a level of recycling is assumed by new legal regulations in Poland), the estimated amount of RA will be about 1.5 million tons in 2022. Assuming a certain underestimation of these forecasts, it should be said that the practical level of recycled aggregate production may be at about 1.8-3.0 million tons

Table 4 Estimates of the CDW generation and production of recycled aggregates [62]

	Year					
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
	Metric tonnes					
Mass of produced waste	4260	4400	4520	4890	5060	5600
Construction materials*	1278	1320	1356	1467	1518	1680
Recycled aggregates*	1150	1188	1220	1320	1366	1512

*at 30% share; ** at 90% recycling

Data compiled by Polish Research Institutions coincide with the estimates of the European Commission, which in a 2011 a consultancy report hired by the European Commission DG ENV [63], included about 4 million tons of CDW generated annually in Poland. As mentioned earlier, due to the high fragmentation of construction waste processing companies and the lack of record-keeping, the amounts of CDW generation are highly estimated. An additional problem is illegal landfilling, the number of which in record 2015 was estimated at more than 16,000. At the same time, the number of legal landfills in Poland does not exceed 300 [64].

In the vicinity of Szczecin, as well as other large agglomerations in the country, there are local companies recycling CDW, mainly in the form of RA, which are used as substrate and sub-soil material in local investments (*Table 5*). Since most often the RA are produced and embedded in a single investment, records of such materials are not kept. The largest companies operating in Poland include BFK Polska Sp. z o.o. in Szczecin, Lafarge Polska and P.P.U. EKO-ZEC Sp. z o.o. which permanently sell RA. Lafarge Polska itself plans to produce 1 million tons of RA by 2030 [65].

Table 5 Use of recycled aggregates in road construction [62]

	Potential material source				
	Wearing course	Binder	Substraction	Sub-soil	Enbankments
Construction and demolition waste					
Aggregate from concrete recycling			+	+	+
Aggregate from brick recycling				+	+
Aggregate from bitumen recycling				+	+
Aggregate from ceramics recycling				+	+

6 Properties of fine recycled aggregates

RECYCL3D will study the incorporation of fRA with grading 0/2 (see the next section). To understand whether fRA produced from mixed CDW have potential to become a standard type of fRA to be used in 3DPC, the project team collected RA produced from mixed CDW and sieved them to the 0/2 size fraction and tested their water absorption and density. These properties were chosen since they correlate well with the quality of aggregates and are a good indicator of the influence of RA in the behaviour of concrete [66].

Table 6 Basic properties of mixed fRA with grading 0/2

Country	Supplier	Grading	Water absorption	Apparent particle density (kg/m ³)	Dry density (kg/m ³)	SSD density (kg/m ³)
Portugal	PT-1	0/2 (sieved from 0/12)	9.7%	2540	2038	2236
	PT-2	0/2 (sieved from 0/12)	8.5%	2219	1867	2026
Poland	CDW 1	0/2 (sieved from 0/90)	8.7%	2590	2120	2236
	CDW 2	0/2 (sieved from 0/90)	9.2%	2449	2110	2212
	CDW 3	0/2 (sieved from 0/63)	8.9%	2327	2050	2178

7 Recommendations for WP2

Based on the main findings of this deliverable, for the activities foreseen on the next Work Packages (WP2 and WP3) it is decided to establish a standard procedure for the whole Consortium related to the production of fRA to be employed as secondary raw materials for the 3DPC mixtures.

More specifically, since the properties presented in Table 6 are not promising for concrete applications, the project will be focused on the production of fRA from well-separated concrete waste. To better understand the influence of the type of waste used, fRA produced from masonry waste will also be analysed. The following consensus was reached:

- The fRA from concrete waste will be produced from “artificial” laboratory-made fine recycled aggregates and the concrete waste will have between 25 MPa and 50 MPa of compressive strength;
- The fRA from masonry waste will be produced from crushed bricks.

Other types of fRA may also be tested, such as MRAs produced from the two aforementioned types of fRA.

The grading of the fRA will be 0/2 mm with removal of fines (fraction below 0.063 mm or that below 0.075 depending on the partner of the consortium).

In a later stage of the consortium the fines will also be tested.

To mitigate the effect of the water absorption of the fRAs on the fresh-state behaviour of concrete, while still benefiting from the hypothetical beneficial effect of the water absorption on buildability,

different moisture conditions of the fRA at the time of mixing will be attempted. In the first iteration, a moisture content equal to 50 % of the 24 h water absorption will be tested.

8 Conclusions

Both fine recycled aggregates and additive manufacturing may decrease the environmental impacts of concrete and their joint use is being studied by RECYCL3D. This concept avoids the downcycling of fine recycled aggregates. Furthermore, for some applications of 3D printed concrete technology the higher water absorption and roughness of fine recycled aggregates in comparison to natural ones may be beneficial and allowing faster prints due to earlier capacity of the concrete mix to withstand new layers of concrete (buildability).

The properties required for a suitable concrete mix for 3D printing differ from those of conventional concrete, since 3D printed concrete needs to be pumpable and extrudable for a relatively long time, at the same time that it must have high early strength and retain its shape. The concepts of pumpability, extrudability, buildability, green strength and open time were presented.

To achieve such properties, the mix design of 3D printed concrete differs relevantly from that of conventional concrete:

- Coarse aggregates are rarely used and, due to technical limitations of pumps and because of the small cross-section of individual layers of concrete, the maximum aggregate size is usually 2 mm or smaller;
- Common binder contents of conventional concrete range between 300 kg/m³ and 420 kg/m³, but those of 3D printed concrete are usually larger than 800 kg/m³;
- Most binder blends include cement and at least two additions, with silica fume and fly ash being the most common;
- The water/binder ratio is very small (usually between 0.21 and 0.35).

Research on 3D printed concrete made with fine recycled aggregates is scarce and the majority of findings are not encouraging, but those investigations were not made with the aim of taking advantage of the properties of fine recycled aggregates. These publications found that the strength of the concrete decreases when recycled aggregates are used and that the rheological properties (which directly affect pumpability, extrudability and open time) decrease. Shrinkage is also affected by the use of fine recycled aggregates and this is, in part, caused by the smaller stiffness of recycled aggregates in comparison to natural ones.

In the aforementioned investigations, the authors argue that the shrinkage of 3D printed concrete increases when recycled aggregates are used because of the water absorbed by the recycled aggregates after mixing. This statement agrees with one of the basic ideas behind this project: currently, the possible advantages of using fine recycled aggregates are not being explored. If the recycled aggregates are moist before being mixed with the other concrete ingredients (e.g. if their moisture is 50% or more of their 24-hour water absorption), early-age shrinkage is expected to decrease due to internal curing, workability may not be relevantly affected (especially if mix design is changed, by instance by increase the content of plasticizers), and buildability may improve (since the recycled aggregates will still absorb part of the mixing water).

Compressive and tensile strength are expected to decrease when fine recycled aggregates are used. Recycled aggregates are weaker than natural ones and the binder pastes of 3D printed concrete have low w/b ratio; therefore, the strength of the aggregates will be a limiting factor.

An appraisal of the current status of CDW valorisation and of the production processes of fine recycled aggregates found that there is legislation for the use of coarse recycled aggregates in conventional concrete; yet the market uptake is low. Currently, producers of recycled aggregates certified for use in concrete are rare. Since this project aims at using fine recycled aggregates, suitable producers of recycled aggregates that could source aggregates to the project are even less.

Common CDW plants were visited and their production process was described. Most plants produce mixed CDW for road construction. A technologically-advanced plant was also visited and produces fine recycled aggregates that are expected to be of high quality.

The project will mainly study two types of recycled aggregate: produced from concrete waste and produced from ceramics. The grading of the aggregates will be 0/2 to conform with the characteristics of the printers used. The incorporation of fines will also be studied.

The next work packages of RECYCL3D are WP2 - *Processing, selection & classification of fRA* and WP3 - *Early-age behaviour, in what concerns the concrete mix design for the 3D-printed concrete mixes*. The titles of the work packages are self-explanatory and the considerations of this report (namely, the types of fine recycled aggregates to be tested and the composition of concrete mixes meant for 3D printing) will be taken into account.

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